

JOURNAL SECTION OR CONFERENCE SECTION

**Evolution of the spatial density of artificial objects
in near-Earth space**

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(Received xx.xx.2025; Revised xx.xx.2025; Accepted xx.xx.2025)

Abstract

The paper discusses the evolution of the distribution density of artificial objects within the navigation and geostationary orbital regions over a 150-year time interval. It demonstrates how this concentration changes due to the introduction of new objects over a 25-year period (from 2000 to 2025) and provides a prediction of potential future density changes.

PACS numbers: Suggested PACS

Keywords: space debris, geostationary area, navigation area, density evolution, equilibrium points

1. INTRODUCTION

The extensive deployment of a large number of Starlink satellites into low-Earth orbit raises acute concerns regarding potential collisions in these orbits and the increasing contamination of the low-Earth orbit (LEO) environment with space debris. However, a similar situation is not unique to LEO. For instance, in navigation orbits, there is already competition for orbital slots for new spacecraft and the challenge of de-orbiting and disposing of decommissioned satellites [1]. In the geostationary region (GEO) objects tend to concentrate around two stable points, at 75 and 225 degrees east longitude, which also leads to an increased density in these areas and a heightened risk of collision [2]. To study this problem, it is reasonable to consider the density distribution of objects in the near-Earth space for the medium-Earth orbit (MEO) and geostationary zones, as modeling the LEO environment over long time intervals is complicated by the significant influence of the atmosphere and the constant need for orbital corrections of these objects.

2. EVOLUTION OF OBJECTS IN THE NAVIGATION AND GEOSTATIONARY ZONES

The exploration of geostationary orbit began in the mid-1960s and continues actively to this day. Fig. 1 illustrates the increasing number of objects in the geostationary and navigation regions, starting from the launch of the first geostationary satellite in 1964. The navigation satellite zone began to be explored much later (from 1977) and is currently represented by

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several constellations: GPS (USA), GLONASS (Russia), Galileo (Europe), and Beidou (China).

Figure 1. Statistics on the number of objects in the navigation and geostationary regions from 1964 to 2025.

In medium-Earth orbits, there were 119 objects in 2000, 235 objects in 2020, and 262 objects in 2025, indicating a two-fold increase in the number of objects over 25 years and a heightened interest in the navigation zone. In the geostationary region, there were 330 objects in 2000, 950 objects in 2020, and 1181 objects in 2025; thus, the number of observed objects has increased nearly four-fold in 25 years. It should be noted that the object data were obtained from space-track.org, which may reflect not only an increase in the number of new satellite launches but also improvements in observation methodologies and in the refinement of orbits for both operational spacecraft and space debris.

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENT

A manifold increase in the concentration of objects within the surveyed zones is predicted to lead to a higher frequency of close approaches and a subsequent alteration in object concentration over 75 and 150 years. To assess these metrics, the following experiment was conducted.

Three distinct groups of objects were analyzed for the navigation and geostationary regions, corresponding to the years 2000, 2020, and 2025. The year 2000 was selected as a baseline,

representing the approximate midpoint of the orbital inclination cycle for geostationary satellites [2]. By this point, the inclination and eccentricity of navigation satellites are expected to have undergone significant changes due to various resonance-induced perturbations [1]. The 2020 satellite constellation status was chosen due to a decreased interest in deploying objects into these orbits and a concurrent rise in the concentration of objects in low-Earth orbit. For all six object sets, orbits were propagated from Two-Line Element (TLE) data to July 1, 2025, using the SGP4 model. Subsequently, the spatial density distribution of these objects was estimated for the years 2025, 2100, and 2175.

From the commencement of the simulation, all objects within the specified regions are treated as passive space objects. Their orbits are not subject to controlled adjustments throughout the modeling period and are characterized by a low area-to-mass ratio (0.01).

To evaluate object concentration, a quantitative search was performed for the number of objects within a defined unit of spatial volume. This volume was delineated by one degree of sub-satellite point latitude, one degree of sub-satellite point longitude, and an altitude of 800 km, which roughly corresponds to one degree of longitude at the sub-satellite point. Object concentration is subject to variation with the altitude of the objects' orbits. In the context of this study, the graphical data presented below represents the maximum concentration recorded across all altitudes within the observed region for a fixed sub-satellite point latitude and longitude.

4. DISTRIBUTION DENSITY OF OBJECTS IN THE NAVIGATION ZONE

A number of studies have been dedicated to the analysis of the dynamic structure of the navigation zone. It has been established that the dynamics of the GLONASS navigation network's operational zone are governed by a single, stable Lidov-Kozai secular resonance, whereas the operational zone of the GPS system is influenced by an orbital resonance and a large number of secular resonances [1]. In the orbital regions of navigation satellites, orbital plane flips can occur, which are transitions from prograde to retrograde motion, caused by solar radiation pressure [4].

Figure 2 shows the distribution density of objects within the navigation zone for the years 2025 (top), 2100 (center), and 2175 (bottom), according to three orbital data sets. The OX and OY axes represent the longitude and latitude of the sub-satellite point, respectively. The OZ axis displays the concentration (quantity) of objects per cubic degree.

It can be noted that a low concentration of objects is observed in the navigation zone; the distribution density of objects rarely exceeds two objects per unit of volume. The operational

Figure 2. Distribution density of objects in the navigation zone for the year 2025 (top), 2100 (center), and 2175 (bottom), according to three orbital data sets: for 2000 (left), 2020 (center), and 2025 (right).

environment in the domain of navigational orbits for the year 2025, considering launches over the past 25 years, remains unchanged and does not alter the assessed probability of collisions between objects in this zone. Taking into account the evolution of the orbits of objects in the navigation zone over 75 and 150 years and the influence of resonances of various natures on the motion of these objects do not significantly change the concentration. All this indicates that the navigation zone is still sparsely populated, and in the near future, the probability of collision between objects is close to zero.

5. DISTRIBUTION DENSITY OF OBJECTS IN THE GEOSTATIONARY ZONE

Figure 3 shows the distribution density of objects within the geostationary zone for the years 2025 (top), 2100 (center), and 2175 (bottom), according to three orbital data sets. The OX and OY axes represent the longitude and latitude of the sub-satellite point, respectively. The OZ axis displays the concentration (quantity) of objects per cubic degree.

Figure 3. Distribution density of objects in the geostationary zone for the year 2025 (top), 2100 (center), and 2175 (bottom), according to three orbital data sets: for 2000 (left), 2020 (center), and 2025 (right).

As can be seen from the Fig. 3, based on the available data sets for the year 2025, the

concentration of objects approximately doubles along the equatorial line. However, after 75 years, calculations of the object distribution density show that objects launched several decades prior (as well as their fragments) will begin to concentrate near the stable libration points of the geostationary orbit (75° E and 255° E). The maximum concentration increases almost threefold, from 18 to 42 objects per unit volume of space, which may indicate a high risk of collision. Although this is not highly prominent in the graphs for the year 2100, the concentration of objects increases not only along the equator (± 5 degrees in sub-satellite point latitude) but also in the region up to ± 15 degrees of sub-satellite point latitude, which also indicates the migration of objects from the equatorial zone. By the year 2175, two dense regions of object distribution are definitively formed near the stable points of the geostationary orbit, and the third cycle of object migration in the geostationary zone concludes, leading to an even greater concentration of objects along the equator. The maximum concentration, as for the year 2100, is 42 objects per unit volume of space, but the overall frequency of object concentration per unit of space increases.

6. CONCLUSION

The density of object distribution in near-Earth space is discussed for the navigation and geostationary orbital regions. The situation in the navigation orbits for 2025, considering recent launches, remains unchanged and does not alter the assessment of collision probability for objects in this zone. The consideration of the orbital evolution of objects in the navigation zone for 75 and 150 years ahead, and the influence of resonances of various natures on the motion of these objects, do not significantly change the concentration. In the geostationary region, the concentration of objects increases along the equatorial line. Subsequently, objects are concentrated near the stable points of the geostationary orbit, with a maximum concentration reaching 42 objects per unit of spatial volume.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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